

WOMEN DISCRIMINATION IN PRIVATE ORGANIZATION

Pradeep Bhanudas Girhe

Abstract

This research will help us to focus on glass ceiling (women Discrimination).It gives us a detailed picture of a role and place of women in the overall privet/corporate sector after we got freedom in India. inthisissue the employment process and other current problems, which women are facing atevery single place, needs to be address immediately. Women, who organize half of humanity, But because of male dominating culture they have to face discrimination, in social as well as economic and political aspects, and since then appeared barriers to their career development. This problem is present even today, in almost across the country. However this problem in privet/Corporate sector appears to becomes more critical. AlsoIn recent period, especially during in 21st era, women 's participation in everyday life has begun to improve in all sectors of life, however it is still far from the desirable place. Our findings, which helped the completion of this research, lead us to

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/eiirj/>

Keywords: discrimination; equality; gender; gender equality; male-controlled; male dominating culture

Introduction

The gender inequality in the allocation of senior positions has also a theoretical explanation. According to the social dominance theory, there are institutional level contributors that help in gender inequality. These contributors influence to further strengthen and maintain the existing inequality of groups. However, the theory explains that these contributors are so deeply rooted in the structures of society that they are no longer seen by the society. In sectors and institutions that are dominated by men, the latter compile vacancy announcements in order to attract the attention of the men only - that eventually helps to preserve gender inequality, keeping women outside areas which are led by men (the dominant group). The main purpose of this research is to identify methods to be used in order to improve the position of women in the private sector.

Understanding of Results

It is already known that the human society consists of male and female, women and men, girls and boys. There are clear biological differences between them, i.e. differences carried from birth, and these differences have originated in the early stages of the human genesis. Therefore we can also say that “sex is determined by biological, natural factors or attributes, i.e. born”. Taking into account these biological differences between the sexes, different theories arise regarding their different social, psychological and economic “differences”. So, theories arise which “proved” the men as more intelligent, stronger, and therefore “naturally” more dominant, based on gender inequality which of course is in favor of men, hence human society must be managed by them. Differences begin from toys that are bought for children, as through them we understand that boys are being prepared by parents for their role outside the house,

whereas the girls for a life that takes place inside the house. Throughout their lives, men and women are pressured to behave as required by the gender differences with a social nature. Therefore men are encouraged to be more active, more decision-makers, more leaders, whereas girls are asked to be more submissive, laconic and serve to others. For women, it is usually thought that they should play a reproductive role, raise and care for children, the elderly, the disabled, to cook and do the housework, whereas the production activities are reserved for men.

Regarding the second hypothesis, which has to do with the women's level of education in comparison to male education, this research showed that women comprise more than 50% of unemployed with low-education (no education or just elementary education). Most of the vacancies for loweducation persons are filled by men, this because these jobs usually require physical skills, for example in construction, and this may be one of the causes for male domination compared to women in the jobs that require low-education. In addition, this situation also results from the fact that women in general are less educated than men.

Conclusion

From the results obtained, we see that women, despite the adoption of high quality laws such as the Law on Labor, Law on protection from discrimination(POSH), etc., which clearly define the role and position of women, i.e. they "disable" gender discrimination of women in daily life, in the field we see that the opposite happens, hence women continue to be discriminated and deprived of many rights, be that their fundamental rights, such as the right to work because these good and quality laws are not implemented, in brief they remain only written on paper. From the results obtained it may be concluded that:

1. Private employers still have male-controlled mentality, considering that women and men are biologically "destined" for certain professions.
2. The unsatisfactory education for women greatly affects the employment of women in the private sector, where women mostly are satisfied with a High School education, as the thought that female is born for biological reproduction and not for economic and scientific achievements is embedded.
3. Laws adopted should quality laws in regards to the role and position of women in privet companies.
4. The salary of women employees in the private sector is not even close to meet their demands, nevertheless they seem to be "satisfied", because they have managed to have a job and this enables them somehow to enjoy the social life, compared to many other women who have little or no such a life at all.

List of references :

- 1) POSH ; (Prevention of Sexual Harassment) Act, 2013
- 2) (1997) 6 SCC 241
- 3) Sec 2(o) of the Act
- 4) Sec 2(n) of the Act
- 5) 2017 SCC Online Del 11327

- 6) Sec 3(2) of the Act
- 7)_ Sec 4 of the Act
- 8) Sec 5, 6 and 7 of the Act
- 9) 2018 SCC Online Del 9340
- 10) Sec 10 of the Act
- 11) Sec 11 of the Act
- 12) Sec 12 of the Act
- 13) Sec 13 of the Act
- 14) Sec 14 of the Act
- 15) Sec 18 of the Act
- 16) Shreya Khaitan, IndiaSpend.com Mar 07, 2021 · 01:30 pm